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Metal-catalysed reactions in the synthesis of heterocyclic structures[†]

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The role of metals in organic synthesis has been well-recognised from the beginning of the development of synthetic procedures in organic chemistry. The group I metals, particularly sodium, have played very significant role in the development of many well known name reactions like Aldol condensation, Claisen condensation, Michael reaction, Dieckman cyclisation and others. Similarly, the group II metals, e.g. magnesium (Grignard reaction) and zinc (Reformatsky reaction) have exerted enormous influence in organic synthetic strategies. However, all these reactions use metals mostly in stoichiometric or, in large proportions. The advent of transition metals like platinum, palladium, ruthenium and others have ushered in a new era in organic synthesis where the metals are used mostly in catalytic amounts. Of these, palladium because of its catalytic role and the capacity to absorb large volumes of hydrogen has been a dominant catalyst in the hydrogenation (carbon-hydrogen bond formation) of organic substrates. More recently, however, palladium has been utilized in carbon-carbon bond formation.

In 1968, Heck¹ published a series of papers showing the formation of carbon-carbon bonds by the reaction between organic halides or triflates and vinylic compounds in the presence of palladium salts as catalysts (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The mechanism of the reaction can be shown as schematically (Scheme 2).

Heck's reaction² between aryl or vinyl halides and vinylic compounds under palladium catalysis has been followed by the extensive application of palladium-catalysed reactions in the synthesis of various carbocycles³ and heterocycles⁴.

In 1975, Cassar⁵ showed that aromatic halides reacted with terminal acetylenes in the presence of tetraakis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(0) and sodium methoxide with the formation of the disubstituted alkynes (Scheme 3).

In the same year, Dieck and Heck⁶ showed that the reaction of terminal alkynes with aromatic halides in the presence of a palladium catalyst in triethylamine at 100 °C yielded disubstituted alkynes (Scheme 4).

A much simplified version for the synthesis of disubstituted alkynes from terminal alkynes was published in 1975 by Sonogashira, Tohda and Hagihara⁷ (Scheme 5).

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Scheme 2

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

In this procedure bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride was used as a catalyst together with cuprous iodide as a co-catalyst in diethylamine as a solvent. The advantage was that the reaction could be carried out at room temperature rather than the high temperature needed

by the Dieck and Heck procedure.

In our work⁸, we have shown that acetylene gas would react with aryl halides in the presence of catalytic amounts of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride and cuprous iodide as a co-catalyst in DMF as solvent and triethylamine as a base to yield disubstituted alkynes in fairly good yields (Scheme 6).

Ar = Ph, *m*-ClC₆H₄, 1-naphthyl, 2-thienyl, 5-CHO-2-thienyl, pyrimidin-5-yl, 5-iodo-1,2,3,4-tetra-hydropyrimidin-2,4-dion-5-yl

X = I, Br

Scheme 6

We have also shown that alk-1-ynes could be coupled⁹ to 1,4-disubstituted 1,3-diynes with bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride and copper(I) iodide in dimethyl formamide in the presence of 4-iodo-2-nitroresorcinol or in dimethyl sulphoxide alone (Scheme 7).

In view of the success of palladium-catalysed reactions in carbon-carbon bond formation, we became inter-

$\text{R}^2 = \text{CMe}_2\text{OH}, \text{CHOHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Me-}p, \text{Ph}, \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}m, 2,4\text{-dimethoxy-pyrimidin-5-yl}, 5\text{-uracilyl}$

Scheme 7

ested to apply this reaction in the synthesis of various heterocyclic structures using terminal alkynes and suitably substituted aryl halides. In this report, we describe our success in this area.

Synthesis of benzo-fused heterocyclic structures with one hetero-atom only

In order to synthesise benzo-fused heterocyclic structures with one hetero-atom only, we reacted aryl halides with a nucleophilic substituent at the *ortho*-position to the halide group on the aromatic ring and reacted them with terminal alkynes in the presence of palladium-copper catalysts and triethylamine in dimethylformamide to yield the heterocycles directly in many cases. In some cases, the disubstituted alkynes were produced which were then cyclised with appropriate reagents to the heterocycles.

(I) Benzo[*b*]furans

Benzo[*b*]furan derivatives¹⁰ have been of importance because of their natural occurrence¹¹⁻¹⁹ and biological properties²⁰. Hence, various classical methods have been developed for elaborating the benzofuran structure¹⁰. Recent efforts involved the use of ketene intermediates²¹, cycloaddition reactions¹⁹, titanium chloride-zinc reagents²², modified Castro reaction²³ and an anionic cycloaddition-thermal cycloreversion strategy²⁴. Various palladium-catalysed syntheses of substituted benzofurans have also been reported²⁵⁻³⁰. The heteroannulation of *o*-iodo phenols with acetylenic substrates containing a terminal acetylenic group leading to substituted benzofurans have been reported by several groups of investigators including ours³¹⁻³⁵.

In our method, a mixture of *o*-iodophenol **13** and an alkyne **14** with a terminal acetylenic function, was heated in the presence of a palladium catalyst, copper(I) iodide

and a base in dimethylformamide giving the 2-substituted benzofurans **15** in excellent yields (61-88%) (Scheme 8).

$\text{R} = \text{Ph}, \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl-}m, \text{CH}_2\text{OH}, \text{CMe}_2\text{OH}, \text{CH}_2\text{OTHP}, \text{CHOH-CH}=\text{CH-Me}, \text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{Ph}, \text{CHOHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{Me-}o, \text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-}p$

Reagents and conditions : (i), $\text{Pd}(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{Cl}_2$ (2-3.5 mol%), CuI (3-5 mol%), DMF, Et_3N ; $T = 60-80^\circ\text{C}$; $t = 16-24$ h.

Scheme 8

Bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride was found to be the catalyst of choice and cuprous iodide was found to be an essential co-catalyst. This catalyst-cocatalyst system was originally suggested by Sonogashira and co-workers⁷. Dimethylformamide was found to be the best solvent due to its ability to solubilise all the starting materials and the catalysts. Triethylamine was used as a base. In our studies, we have used alkynes with a terminal acetylenic group, substituted at the other carbon atom with an alkyl or aryl group, equally satisfactorily. The presence of other functional groups, e.g. hydroxyl, vinyl, aromatic and pyranlyl did not impede the reactions. However, the reaction could not be carried out with a methoxy carbonyl substituent (e.g. propiolic ester).

The products of the reactions were 2-substituted benzofurans although an acyclic intermediate **16** could be isolated in a few cases when tetrabutyl ammonium chloride (PTC) was also used in the reactions. Compound **16** was converted to the corresponding benzofuran by treatment with triethylamine at 60°C for 6 h.

The mechanism of the formation of the benzofurans can be shown as in Scheme 9.

The formation of Pd^0 from the interaction of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride and cuprous acetylide as in step (ii) was proposed by Sonogashira and co-workers⁷. This was also proved from our work⁹ on

Scheme 9

the dimerisation of monosubstituted alkynes to 1,4-disubstituted 1,3-diyne by palladium-copper catalysis. The oxidative addition of *o*-iodophenol to a Pd⁰ complex gives a σ -aryl palladium(II) complex (A) which on *trans* metallation with cuprous acetylide generated the aryl alkynyl palladium(II) species (B). This on reductive elimination of Pd⁰ afforded the acyclic products (C) which on cyclisation in the presence of triethylamine resulted in the formation of the benzofurans.

The method we have described for the synthesis of benzofurans have yielded a number of benzofuran derivatives which have potential as intermediates of naturally occurring compounds³⁶ or of useful biologically active compounds³⁷. The catalytic system of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride-cuprous iodide in the presence of triethylamine in dimethylformamide seems superior to bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) acetate-cuprous iodide in piperidine³¹ for the synthesis of benzofurans.

(II) Phthalides

Compounds containing the phthalide [isobenzofuran-1(3*H*)-one] structure **17** have been the constituents of many

naturally occurring materials, e.g. celery-oil and celery brandy³⁸⁻⁴⁰, dried rhizome of *Lingusticum wallachi*, commonly known as "Senkyu" in Japan⁴¹ and of *Cnidium rhizome* (chuan xing) in Korea⁴². Phthalide-isoquinoline alkaloids have been described by Manske⁴³. The biological activities of 3-alkylidene phthalides have been reported by various investigators⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶.

Over a period of more than a hundred years, a number of methods have been developed for the synthesis of 3-arylidene- or 3-alkylidene phthalides and phthalide containing natural products⁴⁷⁻⁵⁸. However, palladium-catalysed methods for the synthesis of phthalides are limited in number. The thallation-olefination of benzoic acid in the presence of catalytic amounts of palladium reagents usually led to isocoumarins, although phthalides were obtained in a few cases⁵⁹. A two step synthesis involving palladium-catalysed coupling of alkynes with *o*-(iodomethyl)benzoate followed by cyclisation has been reported which led to the synthesis of two phthalides only⁶⁰.

With the purpose of developing a general method for the synthesis of phthalides, we reacted *o*-iodobenzoic acid **18** with terminal alkynes **19-32** under palladium catalysed conditions which led to the phthalides **33-46** as major products (Scheme 10, path a) and to the isocoumarins **47-50** as minor products (Scheme 10, path b)⁶¹. The reactions were usually carried out by heating a mixture of *o*-iodobenzoic acid **18** (2 mol equiv.) and acetylenic compounds **19-32** (4 mol equiv.) in the presence of 0.07 mol equiv. of palladium catalyst, 0.2 mol equiv. of copper(I) iodide and 2 mol equiv. of a base in DMF as solvent. The yields of the compounds are shown under Scheme 10.

Usually the reactions were carried out at 60 °C for 16 h. Bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride was found to be the most effective catalyst and cuprous iodide was found to be an essential co-catalyst. The reactions were usually carried out in DMF as a solvent. The use of other solvents, e.g. DMF-H₂O (2 : 1), benzene or acetonitrile, usually led to poorer yields. However, other considerations, e.g. greater dimerisation of the alkynes (**19**, **20**, **32**) in DMF necessitated the use of acetonitrile as the

(name of R and total yields of phthalide and isocoumarin given)

R = H (19, 33, 27%), Ph (20, 34, 47, 36%), C₆H₄Cl-*m* (21, 35, 68%), 1-naphthyl (22, 36, 61%), CH₂OH (23, 37, 45%), CMe₂OH (24, 38, 48, 73-83%), CHO-CH=CH-Me (25, 39, 49, 78%), CH(OH)Ph (26, 40, 50, 40%), CHOHC₆H₄Me-*o* (27, 41, 63%), CHOHC₆H₄Me-*p* (28, 42, 56%), CHOHC₆H₄OMe-*o* (29, 43, 53%), CHOHC₆H₄OMe-*p* (30, 44, 51%), CHOHC₆H₃(OCH₂O)-3,4 (31, 45, 64%), CO₂Me (32, 46, 69%).

Scheme 10

solvent. Triethylamine was usually the base of choice; however, in case of 32, NaHCO₃ was used since when Et₃N was used, 32 reacted with traces of moisture present leading to its loss.

Terminal alkynes with various alkyl or aryl substituents at the other end did participate in the palladium-catalysed reactions with fair to excellent yields. The reaction was also tolerant of other functional groups present in the alkynes, e.g. aromatic, chloro, hydroxyl, vinyl and ester.

The palladium-catalysed heteroannulation of *o*-iodobenzoic acid with alkynes under our conditions usually led to the formation of the phthalides 33-46 as the major products and the isocoumarins 47-50 as the minor products. In many cases, phthalides were found to be the

exclusive products whereas the isocoumarin 48 was the major product when the reaction was carried out in DMSO. It is to be noted that Liao and Cheng⁶² observed that the reaction of *o*-iodobenzoic acid with terminal alkynes in the presence of palladium catalysts and an equivalent amount of zinc chloride led to the isocoumarins as the major products.

The heteroannulation process was found to be completely stereoselective since only the *Z*-isomers were obtained. The mechanism of the reaction follows the same course as shown in the case of the synthesis of benzofurans (Scheme 9). An open-chain product 51 (in the case of reaction with phenyl acetylene, 20) is suggested as an intermediate. This undergoes cyclisation under the reaction conditions. It appears that the cyclisation was catalysed principally by the conjugate acid of triethylamine with some assistance from the copper(I) ion. The cyclisation of the acyclic compound might yield a five-membered aromatic lactone with an exocyclic double bond (3-ylidene phthalide) or, a six-membered aromatic lactone with the double bond in the endo-position (isocoumarin). Since the formation of the five-membered ring was easier than that of the six-membered ring, the phthalides were obtained as major products (Scheme 11).

We have also reported another convenient and highly regio- and stereo-selective method for the synthesis of (*E*)-3-alkylidene isobenzofuran-1(3*H*)-ones (phthalides)⁶³. 2-Iodobenzyl alcohol 52 (1 mol) on treatment with acetylenic carbinols, 53, (1.5 mol) in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (5 mol%) and copper(I) iodide (8 mol%) in DMF and triethylamine at room temperature for 24 h led to the disubstituted alkynes 54 which on Jones oxidation led to (*E*)-3-alkylidene isobenzofuran-1(3*H*)-ones (phthalides) 55 in good yields in a highly regio- and stereo-selective manner (Scheme 12). It is to be noted that the 3-alkylidene phthalides

Scheme 11

Scheme 12

obtained had the (*E*)-configuration in contrast to the (*Z*)-configuration of the phthalides obtained from Pd-catalysed reactions of *o*-iodobenzoic acid with terminal alkynes (Scheme 10).

(III) Hydroxy chalcones, flavanones and benzo[*b*]furans

Chalcones, flavonoids and benzo[*b*]furans are important groups of compounds which have found widespread occurrence in nature and they are also of great biological importance^{64,65,10}. Many approaches to the synthesis of

chalcones, flavones, flavanones and benzo[*b*]furans have been reported^{65,10,21-24}. Although a number of methods have been developed for the synthesis of benzo[*b*]furans through palladium-catalysed reactions³¹⁻³⁵, palladium-catalysed methods for the synthesis of flavones and flavanones are limited in number⁶⁶. We have developed⁶⁷ a general palladium-catalysed procedure for the synthesis of chalcones, flavanones and benzo[*b*]furans starting from a common precursor, e.g. *o*-iodophenyl acetate (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

When *o*-iodophenyl acetate **56** was reacted with acetylenic carbinols **57** with a terminal acetylenic group in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3 mol%) and cuprous(I) iodide (3 mol%) in DMF in the presence of triethylamine (3 equiv.) as a base at room temperature for 24 h, the substituted carbinols **58** were obtained in excellent yields (72–87%). Both the palladium catalyst and cuprous iodide were found to be essential for the alkylation reactions. The acetoxy alkynols **58** underwent Mayer-Schuster rearrangement in the presence of *p*-TSA in benzene at room temperature to the hydroxy-chalcones **59** which on cyclisation with H₃PO₄-HOAc yielded the corresponding flavanones **60**. A one-pot synthesis of the flavanones could also be achieved by stirring the alkynols **58** with *p*-TSA in benzene at room temperature for 24 h followed by refluxing for 6–8 h. The alkynols **58** also on treatment with sodium ethoxide in ethanol or by heating with palladium acetate (5 mol%) in the presence of LiCl (1 equiv.) and potassium carbonate (2.5 equiv.) in DMF at 80 °C for 16 h yielded the corresponding benzo[*b*]furans **61** in 56–63% yields. The method can be applied for the synthesis of various naturally occurring and biologically important chalcones, flavanones, flavones and benzo[*b*] furans.

(IV) Isoindolin-1-ones

The isoindolin-1-one or 2,3-dihydro-1*H*-isoindol-1-one

(phthalimidine) skeleton is an integral part of many naturally occurring substances⁶⁸ and of biologically active compounds⁶⁹. A number of methods are known for the synthesis of isoindolines and isoindolinones⁷⁰. Only a few examples of palladium-catalysed procedures have appeared⁷¹. We have carried⁷² palladium-catalysed condensation of *o*-iodo benzamides **63** with terminal alkynes **62** and subsequent cyclisation of the products **64** for a regio- and stereo-selective synthesis of isoindolinones **65** (Scheme 14). A few isoquinolinones **66** were also obtained. The reactions were usually carried out by heating a mixture of 2-iodo benzamide or its *N*-substituted derivatives **63** (1 mmol) and alkynes **62** (1.2 mmol) in DMF (5 ml) at 80 °C for 16 h in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine) palladium(II) chloride (2.5 mol%), copper(I) iodide (8 mol%) and triethylamine (4 mmol). The cyclisation of the acyclic products **64** were done by refluxing with sodium ethoxide in ethanol for 4 h. In some cases, the cyclisation was also carried out by heating the open-chain condensation products with Pd^{II} acetate (5 mol%), LiCl (1 mmol) and potassium carbonate (2.5 mmol) in DMF for 16 h at 100 °C. Interestingly, all the isoindolinones have the *Z*-configuration.

We have also developed an alternative 2-step procedure for the synthesis of 3-alkylidene isoindolinones⁷³

Scheme 14

Scheme 15

(Scheme 15).

N-Alkyl or, *N*-aryl-2-iodo benzamides **63** underwent facile reaction with trimethylsilyl acetylene **67** in the presence of $(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{PdCl}_2$ and CuI at room temperature to yield 2-(trimethyl silyl) ethynyl benzamides **68** in excellent yields (83–88%). Compounds **68** were then subjected to Friedel-Crafts reaction with acid-chlorides **69**, or acetic anhydride to afford the 3-alkylidene isoindolinones **71** in overall good yields (46–74%) (Scheme 15). Some of the isoindolinones had the *Z*-configuration ($R_2 = \text{H, C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-}p$) whereas the others had the *E*-configuration ($R_2 = \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-OMe}$).

(V) Quinolines

Many naturally occurring and biologically active quinolines and their perhydro derivatives are known^{74–77}. Classical methods for the synthesis of quinolines have been well reviewed^{74,74b,78}. A few reports on the synthesis of quinolines and quinolones through palladium-catalysed procedures have appeared⁷⁹. We have developed two alternative procedures for the synthesis of quinolines through palladium-catalysed reactions⁸⁰. In the first procedure (method A), a mixture of *o*-iodo anilide **72**, acetylenic

carbinol **57** and $(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{PdCl}_2$ (1–2 mol% based on **72**) in Et_3N was stirred at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere for 24 h yielding the acyclic compounds **73** in moderate to good yields (51–79%) (Scheme 16). An interesting aspect of the condensation reaction is that it did not require CuI as a co-catalyst. The addition of CuI did not improve the yields. Also the condensation reaction could not be carried out with CuI alone. The substituted acetylenic carbinols did not cyclise spontaneously but could be cyclised by refluxing with sodium ethoxide in ethanol for 5 h to 2-aryl quinolines **74** in fair to excellent yields (63–90%) based on **73**. No indole was formed in these cases. In an alternative procedure (method B), *o*-iodoaniline **75** was used as the starting material, obviating the necessity of using expensive trifluoro acetic anhydride to make **72**. The reaction of **75** with acetylenic carbinols **57** in the presence of $(\text{Ph}_3\text{P})_2\text{PdCl}_2$, Et_3N in DMF at room temperature for 24 h yielded the condensation products **76** which after chromatographic purification and subsequent cyclisation with $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (3.5–5 mol%), LiCl (1 equiv.), potassium carbonate (2.5 equiv.) in DMF by heating the mixture at 100 °C for 16 h, yielded the 2-aryl quinolines in good yields (41–60%)

Scheme 16

Scheme 17

(Scheme17).

(VI) *N*-Aryl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1-oxo-isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acids

We have shown that the reaction of 2-iodobenzamides **63** with acetylenic compounds **62** in the presence of palladium-catalysts and subsequent cyclisation led mostly to isoindolinone derivatives **65**. Very few isoquinolinones **66** were obtained (Scheme 14). However, *N*-aryl-2-iodobenzamide **77**, when stirred with methyl acrylate **78** in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3–3.6 mol% based on **77**) in DMF with triethylamine as base, at 80 °C for 24 h gave *N*-aryl-3-methoxy

carbonyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-1(2*H*)isoquinolones **79** together with the deiodinated benzamides **80**⁸¹. Hydrolysis of the esters **79** gave the corresponding acids **81** in 28–71% yields (Scheme 18). It was noticed that bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride was the best catalyst for the condensation reaction. Other palladium catalysts, e.g. palladium(II) acetate or tetrakis(triphenyl-phosphine) palladium(0) resulted in decreased yields. Copper(I) iodide was found not to be essential for the success of the reaction and, in fact, its presence suppressed the yields. DMF was found to be the best solvent for the reactions. It was noted that electron-donating substituents on the *N*-aryl group increased the yield of the cyclised products

Scheme 18

whereas electron-withdrawing substituents decreased the yields. The substitution on the aromatic ring (benzamide part) reduced the yields considerably.

Synthesis of benzo-fused heterocyclic structures with two hetero atoms

(VII) 2,3-Dihydro-2-(ylidene)-1,4-benzo- or naphtho-[2,3-*b*]dioxins

Benzodioxan (2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzodioxin) derivatives are of great significance because of their occurrence in nature^{82,83} and medicinal importance^{84,85}. Various methods⁸⁶ are known for the synthesis of compounds containing the benzodioxan structure. We have developed a palladium-copper catalysed procedure for the synthesis of benzodioxan derivatives⁸⁷. Under this strategy, we have replaced the traditional acetylenic compounds, which we have used for the synthesis of benzofurans, phthalides, flavanones, isoindolinones and quinolines, with mono-prop-2-ynylated catechol **82** or 2-hydroxy-3-(prop-2-ynyloxy) naphthalene **83** and reacted them with an aryl or heteroaryl or alkenyl halide **84** in the presence of bis(triphenyl phosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3.5 mol%) and cuprous iodide (7 mol%) in triethylamine at room temperature for 20 h followed by heating at 100 °C for 16 h, to afford a regio- and stereo-selective formation of (*Z*)-2,3-dihydro-2-(ylidene)-1,4-benzodioxins **85** or naphtho[2,3-*b*]dioxins **86** in good yields (Scheme 19).

Bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride was found to be the catalyst of choice. Also, cuprous iodide was needed as an essential co-catalyst. This reaction was also applied using a variety of aromatic diiodides under palladium-copper catalysis condition leading to the formation of a number of bis-heteroannulated products of *Z*-stereochemistry (Scheme 20).

The reactions were found to be completely regio- and stereo-selective and only the *Z*-isomers were obtained. No seven membered ring or endo isomer was isolated.

Mechanistically, the formation of (*Z*)-2,3-dihydro-2-(ylidene)-1,4-benzo- and naphthodioxins could be explained as depicted in Scheme 21.

The Pd⁰ is formed from the oxidative dimerisation of the terminal acetylenic compound. The oxidative coupling of Pd⁰ with RX generates the palladium species RPdX which on interaction with the copper salt A de-

Reagents and conditions :

(i) 3.5 mol% (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂, 7 mol% CuI, Et₃N, stirring at room temperature for 20 h followed by heating at 100 °C for 16 h.

- 84a**, R = Ph
- 84b**, R = 1-Naphthyl
- 84c**, R = CH=CH-C₆H₅
- 84d**, R = 2-Thienyl
- 84e**, R = 5-Formyl-2-thienyl
- 84f**, R = 2,4-Dimethoxy-5-pyrimidinyl
- 84g**, R = 2-Nitro-4-methylphenyl
- 84h**, R = 2-MeOC₆H₄
- 84i**, R = 3-ClC₆H₄
- 84j**, R = 2-NO₂-C₆H₄
- 84k**, R = 2-MeOCOC₆H₄
- 84l**, R = 5-Iodo-2-thienyl
- 84m**, R = 4-IC₆H₄
- 84n**, R = 4'-IC₆H₄-C₆H₄
- 84o**, R = 2-IC₆H₄

Scheme 19

Scheme 20

Scheme 21

rived from **82** or **83**, gives rise to the palladium alkynyl species **B**. The extrusion of Pd^0 from **B** will lead to **D** which on cyclisation would generate the benzo- or naphthodioxan derivatives **85** or **86** respectively. Alternatively, **B** could lead to **C** which on extrusion of Pd^0 will generate compounds **85** or **86**.

(VIII) 3,4-Dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazines

The 2H-1,4-benzoxazine structure has been the integral part of many naturally occurring substances⁸⁸. Blepharin, [(2R)-2- -D-glucopyranosyloxy-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3(4H)-one] **87** and other glycosides of 2-hydroxy-2H-1,4-benzoxazine-3(4H)-one skeleton have been found to occur in gramineous plants such as maize, wheat, rye, rice, etc.⁸⁹.

Similarly, actinomycin D, an anticancer drug isolated from streptomycetes, has the benzoxazine structural moiety as part of the chromophoric unit of the drug molecule⁹⁰. Various other benzoxazine derivatives have also shown to have interesting pharmacological properties⁹¹. In view of the importance of the 2H-1,4-benzoxazine structure, several syntheses of this compound and its derivatives have been reported^{88,92}.

We have developed a palladium-copper catalysed procedure for the synthesis of (Z)-4-alkyl-2-alkyl(aryl)idene-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazines **91** and (Z)-3-alkyl(aryl)idene-4-tosyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazines **97**⁹³.

2-[N-Alkyl (or benzyl)-N-prop-2'-ynyl]aminophenyl tosylate **88** was treated with aryl iodides **89** in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3 mol%) and cuprous iodide (5 mol%) in triethyl amine at room temperature for 16 h when the disubstituted alkynes **90** were produced. These did not undergo cyclisation under the palladium-copper catalysis condition but could be

Ar = Aryl or heteroaryl; R = Bn, Me or Et

Reagents and conditions :

- (i) $(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{PdCl}_2$ (3.0 mol%), CuI (5 mol%), Et_3N (12 mL), stirring at room temperature, 16 h.
 (ii) KOH (19 equiv.), EtOH/ H_2O , 80 °C, 8–10 h.

Scheme 22

cyclised with KOH in ethanol/ H_2O under reflux for 8–10 h to the (*Z*)-2-alkylidene-4-alkyl(benzyl)-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazines **91** in excellent yields (59–85%) (Scheme 22). The heteroannulation process was found to be completely regio- and stereo-selective. No seven-membered ring compound or compounds of *E*-stereochemistry were isolated. The mechanism of the reaction is similar to that we have proposed for the synthesis of 2,3-dihydro-1,4-benzodioxins as in Scheme 21.

The regio-isomers of compounds **91**, e.g. (*Z*)-3-alkylidene-4-tosyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazines **97** were also synthesized through palladium-copper catalysed reactions as shown in Scheme 23.

It is of interest to note that the free-amines **95** could not be cyclised under various conditions. Hence, **95** were converted to the tosylates **96** which could then be very simply cyclised with CuI in the presence of potassium carbonate and tetrabutyl ammonium bromide in acetonitrile by heating at 80 °C. 3-Alkylidene-4-tosyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1,4-benzoxazines **97**, in contrast to the regio-isomers **91**, were found to be stable in chloroform and on the silica gel column. Compounds **97** were found to be of the *Z*-stereochemistry. Thus a highly successful general method for the synthesis of 2-alkylidene and 3-alkylidene-3,4-dihydro-2H-benzo-1,4-oxazines through palladium-copper catalysed reactions has been developed. The method is characterized by the use of readily available inexpensive starting materials, non-hazardous reagents, mild reaction conditions and relatively good to excellent yields of products. The method is also highly regio- and stereo-selective in nature.

(IX) Benzodioxepinones and benzoxazepinones

A highly regio- and stereo-selective synthesis of (*Z*)-3-arylidene-2,3-dihydro-5H-1,4-benzodioxepin-5-ones and (*Z*)-3-arylidene-1,2,3,5-tetrahydro-4,1-benzoxazepin-5-

Reagents and conditions : (i) Propargyl bromide (1.2 equiv., 43.08 mmol), K_2CO_3 (35.9 mmol), in acetone (40 mL), reflux, 16 h. (ii) Fe in acetic acid. (iii) ArI (0.83 equiv., 2.03 mmol), $(\text{PPh}_3)_2\text{PdCl}_2$ (0.06 mmol), CuI (0.1 mmol), Et_3N (12 mL). (iv) Tosyl chloride (1.0 equiv., 1.3 mmol), Py (1.3 mmol), CH_2Cl_2 (9 mL), rt, 2 h. (v) CuI (20 mol%), K_2CO_3 (2.5 equiv.), Bu_4NBr (1 equiv.), CH_3CN (11 mL), 12 h, 80 °C.

Scheme 23

ones through palladium-copper catalysed reactions have been reported by Kundu and Chaudhuri⁹⁴. Sodium 2-(prop-2'-ynyloxy) benzoate **98** was treated with aryl iodides **100** in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine) palladium(II) chloride (2.5 mol%) as catalyst and copper(I) iodide (5 mol%) as co-catalyst, triethylamine (2.5 equiv.) as base in acetonitrile and DMF mixture at room temperature for 24 h in an argon atmosphere to afford 2-[(3'-aryl)prop-2'-ynyloxy]benzoic acids **101**. These acids were then cyclised with copper(I) iodide (5 mol%) and triethylamine (4 equiv.) in dry acetonitrile at 80 °C under argon atmosphere for 16 h to yield (*Z*)-3-arylidene-2,3-dihydro-5*H*-1,4-benzodioxepin-5-ones (**103**, where X = O). Similarly, starting from **99**, (*Z*)-3-arylidene-1,2,3,5-tetrahydro-4,1-benzoxazepin-5-ones (**104**, where X = N-Bu) were obtained (Scheme 24).

benzamide **105a** or, 2-(*N*-benzyl-*N*-prop-2'-ynyl)amino-*N*'-*p*-tolyl benzamide **105b** were reacted with aryl iodides **106** in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine) palladium(II) chloride (2.5 mol%), cuprous iodide (5 mol%), triethyl amine (5 equiv.) in acetonitrile at room temperature for 16 h to yield the disubstituted alkynes **107** in good yields. Both the palladium catalyst and CuI were found to be essential for the *C*-arylation of the terminal alkynes. The disubstituted alkynes did not cyclise spontaneously but could be cyclised with CuI (20 mol%) in the presence of potassium carbonate (2.5 equiv.) and tetrabutyl ammonium bromide (1 equiv.) by heating in acetonitrile at 80 °C for 16–24 h. In most of the cases, the (*E*)-2-(arylviny)quinazolines **108** (Ar = Ph, C₆H₄Me-*o*, C₆H₄OMe-*p* etc.) were formed in a highly regio- and

Scheme 24

(X) (*E*)-2-(2-Arylviny)quinazolines

The quinazoline structure⁹⁵ has been the integral part of many naturally occurring⁹⁶ and biologically active compounds⁹⁷. In view of the importance of quinazoline structure, many classical methods of its synthesis have been reported⁹⁸. Recently, we have reported⁹⁹ general palladium and copper catalysed procedure for the synthesis of 2-substituted-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-ones **108** (Scheme 25).

2-(*N*-Methyl-*N*-prop-2'-ynyl)amino-*N*'-*p*-tolyl

stereo-selective manner. Only in a few cases, small amounts (7–10%) of the benzodiazepinones **109** were formed.

(XI) 1,3-Benzothiazolines

1,3-Benzothiazoles and benzothiazolines (2,3-dihydrobenzothiazoles)¹⁰⁰ are of importance because of their extensive occurrence in nature¹⁰¹ and significant biological properties¹⁰². Various methods for the synthesis of benzothiazoles and benzothiazolines have been reported in literature¹⁰³. We have recently described¹⁰⁴ a

Reagents and conditions :

(i) (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (2.5 mol%), CuI (5 mol%), Et₃N (5 eq.), CH₃CN, rt, 16 h.

(ii) CuI (20 mol%), K₂CO₃ (2.5 eq.), Bu₄NBr (1 eq.), CH₃CN, 80 °C, 16–24 h.

108, R = Me, Ar = Ph, C₆H₄Me-*o*, C₆H₄OMe-*o*, C₆H₄OMe-*p*, C₆H₄CO₂Me-*o*, 2-thienyl, 2,4-dimethoxypyrimidin-5-yl.

108, R = Bn, Ar = C₆H₄Me-*o*, C₆H₄Me-*p*, C₆H₄Cl-*m*, C₆H₄CO₂Me-*o*, 2-thienyl, 2,4-dimethoxypyrimidin-5-yl.

109, R = Bn, Ar = C₆H₄Me-*p*, C₆H₄Cl-*m*, 2-thienyl.

Scheme 25

novel, general and convenient palladium-copper catalysed procedure for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoline derivatives. 3-(2-Aminophenylthio)prop-1-yne **110** reacted with aryl iodides **111** in the presence of bis(triphenyl phosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3 mol%) as catalyst, copper(I) iodide (6 mol%) as a co-catalyst and triethylamine (4 equiv.) as a base in acetonitrile at room temperature for 24 h. Under the reaction conditions, the nor-

mal C-arylation of the terminal alkynes **110** took place yielding the disubstituted alkynes **112** which, in the form of the tosylates, could be cyclised to (*E*)-2-(2-arylvinyl)-3-tosylbenzothiazolines **113** by reflux in THF for 36 h in the presence of CuI (40 mol%) and triethylamine (4 equiv.) in fairly good yields (63–80%) rather than the expected 3-alkylidene-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzothiazines **114** (Scheme 26).

Ar = C₄H₅, 1-naphthyl, 3-ClC₆H₄, 2-MeC₆H₄, 4-MeC₆H₄, 4-MeOC₆H₄, 2-MeOCOC₆H₄, 2-thienyl etc.

Reagents and conditions : (i) (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (3 mol%), CuI (6 mol%), triethylamine, CH₃CN, rt, 24 h. (ii) *p*-TsCl, py, CH₂Cl₂, rt, 10 h. (iii) CuI (40 mol%), Et₃N, THF, reflux, 36 h.

Scheme 26

It is to be noticed that for the cyclisation step, considerable amount of CuI (40 mol%) and triethylamine (4 equiv.) were needed to get the optimum yields of the products.

Mechanistically, the formation of the benzothiazolines **113** could be explained on the basis (i) the usual Pd⁰-mediated C-arylation (Sonogashira reaction) leading to the disubstituted alkynes **112**, (ii) subsequent isomerisation of the corresponding propargylic tosylates **112a** to the allenic intermediates **112b**¹⁰⁵, (iii) which then underwent cyclisation¹⁰⁶ to (*E*)-2-(2-aryl vinyl)-3-tosylbenzothiazolines **113** (Scheme 27).

Scheme 27

(XII) 1,4-Benzothiazines

The natural occurrence¹⁰⁵, biological activities¹⁰⁶ and methods for the synthesis¹⁰⁷ of 1,4-benzothiazines have been reported. We have recently developed^{104b} a general procedure for the synthesis of 2-alkyl(aryl)idene-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-benzothiazines. *S*-[2-(*N*-Prop-2'-ynyl)aminophenyl]-*N,N*-dimethyl thiocarbamate **117** reacted with aryl iodides **118** in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3.5 mol%), copper(I) iodide (6 mol%) and triethylamine in acetonitrile at room temperature for 24 h yielding the disubstituted alkynes **119** (Scheme 28).

Compounds **119** and the corresponding *N*-Me or, *N*-Bu derivatives could be cyclised with KOH in MeOH

under reflux for 24 h to the 2-alkyl(aryl)idene-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-1,4-benzothiazines **121-123**.

Mechanistically, the terminal alkyne **117** underwent the usual C-arylation catalysed by Pd⁰ generated from bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride leading to the disubstituted alkynes **119** which on cyclisation with KOH afforded the 2-alkylidene benzothiazines **121** of *E*-configuration. No compounds of *Z*-configuration were obtained. This could result from the syn-addition caused by an exo-dig attack on the alkyne moiety by the thiol group resulting from the alkaline hydrolysis of the -SCONMe₂ group (Scheme 29).

(XIII) Benzoxathiinones

3,1-Benzoxathiin-4-ones have been extensively studied and synthesized by several workers¹⁰⁸. Recently, we have reported¹⁰⁹ a novel strategy for the synthesis of (*E*)-2-(2-arylvinyl)-3,1-benzoxathiin-4-ones **126** starting from 3-[(2-methoxycarbonyl)phenylthio]propyne **124** and aryl iodides **118** using palladium- and copper-mediated reactions (Scheme 30).

3-[2-Methoxycarbonyl)phenylthio]propyne **124** reacted with aryl iodides **118** in the presence of bis(triphenylphosphine)palladium(II) chloride (3.5 mol%), copper(I) iodide (6 mol%) and triethylamine (4 equiv.) in acetonitrile at room temperature for 24 h in an argon atmosphere to yield the disubstituted alkynes **125**. The disubstituted alkynes were then hydrolysed with 5 *M* methanolic KOH solution by stirring at room temperature for 2 h

Reagents and conditions :

- (i) Fe in AcOH.
- (ii) Propargyl bromide, K₂CO₃, acetone, reflux, 16 h.
- (iii) (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂, CuI, Et₃N, CH₃CN, rt, 24 h.
- (iv) RX, K₂CO₃, acetone, reflux, 10 h.
- (v) KOH in MeOH, reflux, 24 h.

Scheme 28

followed by acidification [dil. HCl (1 : 1)] to the carboxylic acids, which were then heated under reflux in the presence of copper(I) iodide (20 mol%) and triethylamine in THF for 24 h in an argon atmosphere. (*E*)-2-(2-Arylviny)-3,1-benzoxathiin-4-ones **126** were formed in a completely regio- and stereo-selective manner instead

of the expected seven-membered heterocyclic compounds, i.e. benzoxathiinones **127** (Scheme 30). The stereochemistry around the double bond was the *E*-configuration on the basis of the coupling constants (15 Hz) of the two vinylic protons.

Allenic intermediates **128** were formed in all the cases

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Scheme 29

Reagents and conditions : (i) K₂CO₃, propargyl bromide, acetone, reflux, 16 h. (ii) (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (3.5 mol%), CuI (6 mol%), Et₃N, CH₃CN, rt, 24 h. (iii) 5 M Methanolic KOH, rt, 2 h. (iv) HCl (1 : 1). (v) CuI (20 mol%), Et₃N, THF, reflux, 24 h.

Scheme 30

due to the alkaline hydrolysis of compounds **125**. The allenic intermediates then underwent cyclisation to the 3,1-benzoxathiin-4-ones **126**.

128

Ar = Ph, C₆H₄Me-*p*, C₆H₄OMe-*o*, 2-naphthyl

(XIV) 2-Aryl quinoxalines

Biologically active compounds containing the quinoxaline ring have been reported in literature¹¹⁰. There have been various methods for the synthesis of quinoxaline compounds¹¹¹. We have recently reported a very simple procedure for the synthesis of 2-aryl quinoxalines¹¹². The terminal alkyne **129** underwent the usual *C*-arylation reaction with aryl iodides **118** in the presence of (PPh₃)₂PdCl₂ (3 mol%), CuI (8 mol%), triethylamine (5 mmol) in acetonitrile at room temperature for 24 h to yield the disubstituted alkynes **130** in moderate to good yields (43–65%). These were then cyclised with CuI (10 mol%) in the presence of potassium carbonate (2 mmol) in DMF by heating at 100 °C for 24 h. But interestingly, instead of the expected 2-alkylidene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro quinoxaline **131**, the 2-aryl quinoxalines **132** were formed in good yields (Scheme 31).

For C–C bond formation both the palladium catalyst and CuI were needed whereas for cyclisation, only CuI was needed and was found to be essential. The absence of CuI did not give any cyclic product. Similarly, potassium carbonate was found to be essential for the reaction. Its replacement with triethylamine failed to yield the cyclic products **132**.

(XV) 2-Alkyl(aryl)idene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydro quinoxalines

In continuation of the arylation and heteroannulation studies of **129** with aryl iodides **118** under palladium-catalysis, we were surprised to find¹¹³ that the 2-alkyl(aryl)idene-1,2,3,4-tetrahydroquinoxalines **131** could be obtained smoothly in a single step operation when the reaction was carried out in the presence of a phase transfer catalyst¹¹⁴, e.g. Bu₄NBr (0.5 equiv.) and potassium carbonate (5 equiv.) in DMF at room temperature for 24 h (Scheme 32).

The reaction was solely catalysed by palladium acetate along with Bu₄NBr. Most interesting, there was no need for cuprous iodide¹¹⁵ or triphenyl phosphine. Also, in contrast to the syntheses of benzoxazines, benzodioxepinones, benzoxazepinones and 2-aryl quinoxalines, the formation of 2-alkyl(aryl)idene quinoxalines was an one step process. The arylation of the terminal alkynes was followed by concurrent cyclisation leading to the quinoxalines. Interestingly, the 2-alkyl(aryl)idene

Scheme 31

Reagents and conditions :

(i) Pd(OAc)₂, Bu₄NBr, K₂CO₃, DMF, rt, 24 h.

Scheme 32

quinoxalines were of the *E*-configuration instead of the usually expected *Z*-configuration.

Conclusion :

We have described procedures for carbon-carbon bond formation by using terminal alkynes and aryl halides in the presence of palladium catalysts and cuprous iodide as co-catalyst (Sonogashira reaction) in most of the cases. But in some cases, cuprous iodide as a co-catalyst was not needed (non-Sonogashira reaction). The products which have an adjacent nucleophilic group were then cyclised leading to various heterocyclic structures, e.g. benzofurans, phthalides, flavanones, isoindolinones, quinolines, benzodioxans, benzoxazines, benzodioxepinones, benzoxazepinones, benzothiazolines, benzothiazines, benzoxathiinones, quinazolinones and quinoxalines. A procedure for the synthesis of isoquinoline carboxylic acids using vinylic compounds and aryl iodides has also been reported.

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